

Tools	Explanation	Examples	
Open Refine	Often mentioned data wrangling tool		
Wikis		ScraperWiki, JamWiki	
Open Data Repositories		CKAN	
Sheet Software		Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets	
Translation Software	To automatically translate data	Google Translate, Microsoft Translator	
Auth Providers	Auth providers to access data that needs an	Twitter, LinkedIn, Google, Facebook	
Databases	Database software, SQL/NoSQL	PostgreSQL, MongoDB	
CLI tools		ftp, wget, rsync, http	
Statistical computing languages		R, Matlab, Octave	
Domain specific languages		Awk	
Visualization tools		Tableau, Fusion Tables, GnuPlot	
GitHub	Collaboration hub for source code		
Travis	CI system		
git	Collaboration and versioning tool		
Official discussion board	Discussion software provided by publisher		
Kaggle	Platform hosting data science competitions		
General purpose programming language		Python, java, C, Ruby, PHP, Perl, Scala, Javascript	
Data Science Libraries		Pandas, scikit-learn, Keras, AutoML	
Domain specific software packages		ODToolkit, obFMU, PAD	
Blogs / Websites	To discover/discuss data or provide documentation		
Big data processing tools		Hadoop, Spark, Starfish, EpiC	
Notebooks		Jupyter, Binder	